

IOT-ENABLED REAL TIME MONITORING AND CONTROL OF INDUCTION MOTOR

N. Rajesh Babu¹, M. Shakuntala², J. Pravarsha³, M.Narendra Gopi⁴, P. Venkateswarao⁵

¹ N. Rajesh Babu, *EEE & PSCMR college*

² M. Shakuntala *EEE & PSCMR college*

³ J. Pravarsha *EEE & PSCMR college*

⁴ M. Narendra Gopi *EEE & PSCMR college*

⁵ P. Venkateswara *EEE & PSCMR college*

Abstract

Induction motors have become the most used motors in industrial applications in recent years. However, despite their high reliability, operating conditions can expose induction motors to various fault conditions. Implementing condition monitoring is crucial to prevent unexpected motor shutdowns and enhance the motor's productivity and lifespan. One effective approach to monitoring is leveraging the Internet of Things (IoT), which enables real-time data collection, data visualization through graphs, and the development of web services and connections. The objective of this research is to monitor real-time data and detect electrical faults in a three-phase induction motor. The monitored electrical parameters include voltage, current, and temperature. The system will identify faults such as overcurrent, overvoltage, undervoltage, undercurrent, and overtemperature. Once a fault is detected, the system will isolate the motor to prevent further damage. Additionally, the system will utilize the Internet of Things to measure and display electrical parameters, including voltage, current, and temperature, along with their corresponding graphs, through a mobile application. Data transmission between the system and the mobile application will occur between 7-8 a.m. and 9-10 p.m. The mobile application will access a history log, allowing users to review past data. Furthermore, the application will compile information about motor faults that occurred on specific days and times, which will be displayed in the error logs.

Key Words: Fault Detection, Electrical Parameters, Improve efficiency, Induction motors, IOT, Cloud space

1.INTRODUCTION

Asynchronous motors, commonly called induction motors, are electromechanical machines that convert electrical energy into mechanical energy. A three-phase induction motor is a widely used system due to its reliability, low cost, and high performance, making it the most common type of AC motor in industrial and commercial applications. These motors have a wide range of uses, from low-power applications in households to large-scale applications in power plants. Despite their high reliability, induction motors can experience various fault conditions under different operating conditions. Undetected faults can lead to motor malfunctions, which present a significant problem in industries and other fields where

induction motors are commonly employed. Motor failures can cause production shutdowns and loss of processing time. Therefore, it is crucial to protect against these faults to ensure uninterrupted operations. Continuous monitoring of induction motors is necessary to detect faults at an early stage and take appropriate corrective actions promptly. Early fault detection improves efficiency, minimizes energy usage, reduces repair and service costs, extends the motor's life cycle, and enhances safety, resulting in significantly reduced lifetime costs. The most common external faults encountered by induction motors include overcurrent, undercurrent, overtemperature, overvoltage, and undervoltage. Mobile phones have become an integral part of people's daily lives, offering diverse applications and gradually replacing many other devices. Mobile technology has evolved from basic communication to multitasking systems used for GPS navigation, internet browsing, gaming, and more. Mobile phones are an ideal platform for utilizing the Internet of Things (IoT). In this study, we will access the IoT through a mobile application that allows users to view the electrical parameters of the three-phase induction motor.

The objectives of this study are as follows:

1. Develop a system for measuring voltage, current, and temperature to detect faults.
2. Create a mobile application for viewing graphs and measuring voltage, current, and temperature.
3. Classify specific faults such as overvoltage, undervoltage, overcurrent, undercurrent, and overtemperature based on parameter readings.
4. Evaluate the system's accuracy and reliability using a confusion matrix to determine if it properly monitors and detects the electrical parameters and faults.

This study also aims to provide an improved monitoring and protection system for three-phase induction motors, particularly in large-scale applications such as industrial plants. The monitoring system will focus on measuring motor parameters such as voltage, current, and temperature. It should be noted that the fault detection system does not encompass all possible faults that may occur in the motor, such as mechanical and environmental faults. The electrical faults that will be tested include overvoltage, undervoltage, overcurrent, undercurrent, and overtemperature

2. 2. Related works

Induction motors are widely used in the industry due to their durability and ease of use [1]. During the operation of these motors, various types of faults or irregular conditions can occur

[2]. One such condition is overcurrent, which happens when a conductor carries a higher electric current than expected. This can lead to excessive heat generation and the risk of fire or equipment damage. The overcurrent limit is set at 1.2 times the nominal operating current [2]. Conversely, undercurrent occurs when a conductor carries a smaller electric current than expected in an electric power system [3]. Overvoltage is another fault that occurs when the voltages of the three phases exceed the rated voltage. This can increase current flow and stress on the motor insulation due to high heat dissipation. Conventional protection systems use overvoltage relays to safeguard the motor [1]. On the other hand, undervoltage occurs when the motor is connected to a power supply with a lower voltage than expected. Undervoltage causes an increase in motor current, rated copper losses, and winding temperature [4]. Conventional systems use low-voltage relays, but they require a delay mechanism to prevent undesired relay shutdowns due to instantaneous voltage decreases. These mechanisms rely on highly sensitive devices with calibration [5]. In the maintenance of electrical equipment, early detection of incipient faults is crucial. Condition monitoring of three phase induction motors is particularly important due to their widespread use in modern industries [6]. Conventional protection systems for three-phase induction motors typically rely on a combination of mechanical and electrical devices, which can respond slowly compared to electronic devices. Moreover, this method is expensive and takes up a lot of space [7]. A study proposed a protection system for three-phase induction motors against overvoltage and undervoltage [8]. Its circuit, controlled by a microcontroller, constantly monitors the voltages of the three phases. If any abnormal voltage is detected, the motor is turned off until it returns to normal. Fault conditions are displayed on an LCD monitor. However, their work only focused on monitoring two electrical faults, while three-phase induction motors commonly experience other faults such as overtemperature, overcurrent, and undercurrent. The Internet of Things (IoT) connects sensors and actuators in physical objects through wired and wireless networks, generating large amounts of data that can be analyzed by computers. This technology has been used in industrial automation to monitor and detect faults in induction motors, thereby increasing productivity

3.Methodology

Fig -1: Framework

Figure 1 shows the conceptual framework of the system where the input, process, and output are shown. The input consists of gathering the measurements of the motor's parameters. The

gathered data will then be processed to check and compare whether there is an abnormal condition present in the system Figure 3 shows the circuit design and the corresponding actual system prototype. The control mechanism used is the Arduino, a microcontroller that is powered by the power supply, sensors for input devices, parameter display, and fault detection for the output. The connections have been formed through the Arduino between the input devices and the output devices. The sensor unit detects and feeds the corresponding motor parameters to the Arduino parameters and fault alert will be displayed through a liquid crystal display (LCD) and a mobile application. Lastly, the motor will be cut off from the source.

B. System Block diagram

Fig -2: System Block Diagram

Figure 2 shows the Systems block diagram. The system is made up of sensors and a power supply as inputs that are connected to the microcontroller, Arduino Mega, and a relay and contactor as outputs that serve as protection when the motor experiences abnormal conditions. The microcontroller is also linked to the Wi-Fi module supplied by the buck converter to the IoT server, which is then linked to the mobile application to display and alert the user of the motor's condition. Another output is the LCD, which displays the parameters and faults. The diagram below shows the overall circuit diagram and the actual system design.

A. Prototype Development

1) Prototype

According to the instructions given, Arduino reads the data from different sensors, analyses and compares the data from the limit, and then sends the sensor information to the output. In the parameter display, the motor parameters and their trends are displayed. These parameters will determine if the motor is experiencing a fault. Once a fault is detected, a warning will be displayed, and the motor will immediately be cut off from the

source. Furthermore, the history and error logs will be displayed in the mobile application as well with its specific date and time.

2) Software Development

Fig. 4. The Algorithm Flow Chart

Figure 4 shows the flow chart of the algorithm used in this study. In setting the parameters, the first option that will appear on the LCD screen is Enter or Escape. The previously saved input limits will be shown when Escape is selected. Voltage, current, and temperature are the three parameters that are displayed when Enter is pressed. Once Voltage is selected, the measured per-phase voltages are displayed, and the upper and lower limits can be adjusted. The limits will be saved and displayed once the user is done setting them. To get back to the main menu, press the Escape key. The current and temperature work in the same way. The sensor that collects data is the input. The gathered data is then compared to the input limits. The system is experiencing a fault if the measured data exceeds the upper limit. The motor's supply will be shut off, and an LCD display will indicate the fault type and its phase. If the sensor data is below the lower limit, the same result will be achieved. If there were no errors, the system would keep monitoring. After that, the data will be sent to the Wi-Fi module, then to Firebase, and lastly to the mobile application.

4.Results and Discussion

Figure 5 illustrates the data collection flowchart, which outlines the process. It begins with the Wi-Fi module connecting to the network and obtaining the date and time. Next, the data sent by the microcontroller is examined and evaluated to identify any faults. If there are no errors, the data length is examined and classified by parameter. Afterward, the data is transferred to the Firebase folder. However, data transmission to the mobile application only occurs between 7-8 a.m. and 9-10 p.m. to prevent data overload.

The results presented above demonstrate the corrective actions taken when measured voltages exceed 240 volts (overvoltage) and 215 volts (undervoltage). Similar results were obtained when measured currents and temperature surpassed

Fig. 5. Data Collection Flowchart

1.79 amperes (undercurrent), 1.9 amperes (overcurrent), and 40.40 degrees Celsius (overtemperature). In fault cases, the motor is isolated using a contactor, and the fault is displayed on the LCD.

Once a fault is identified, the microcontroller's data length is evaluated to determine whether it is 1 or 0. If it is 1, the data indicates a fault in the motor, and its position is read to determine the type and phase of the fault. This information is then transmitted to the Firebase folder and subsequently to the mobile application. On the other hand, if a data value of 0 is read, it indicates that the system is functioning properly. Table 1 below presents the system's fault detection capabilities by comparing the number of times corrective actions were taken after detecting a fault. If the motor is disconnected from the power supply, the data passes the test; otherwise, it fails. Based on the reliability computation formula, the system is deemed completely reliable.

Data from multiple tests conducted in 30 trials indicate that the system consistently responded correctly to each test and successfully transferred data to the mobile application. The summarized results of different scenarios are tabulated in Table 1, demonstrating a 100% success rate with zero failures across all trials. The data presented in Tables 2-6 are obtained from 30 trials conducted for four different scenarios involving over and under voltages, currents, and temperatures. Due to space limitations, only a few trials are included in the tables, but they are representative of the overall results. It is evident that there is no significant difference between the measured data from the sensors and the data obtained from the

multimeter readings. The system exhibited consistent and precise data-gathering capabilities, as shown in Tables 2-6 in the appendices.

Table -1: Sample Table format

Table 1
Reliability of the System to Detect Faults

Corrective Action Applied On	Pass	Fail
Overvoltage	30	0
Undervoltage	30	0
Overcurrent	30	0
Undercurrent	30	0
Over Temperature	30	0

$$Reliability = \frac{Pass}{Pass + Fail} \times 100\%$$

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

The researchers successfully developed a monitoring system for three-phase motor parameters, including voltage, current, and temperature. Additionally, the system could detect specific types of faults and take corrective action when necessary. The measured parameters could be monitored through an LCD and mobile application. Furthermore, the researchers were able to collect data on motor faults occurring at specific times during the day. Compared to traditional systems, this device offered a wider range of fields, real-time data viewing, graphs, and efficient monitoring, effectively incorporating the concept of the Internet of Things for remote monitoring.

Following the measurement accuracy test, the researchers established that their system provided accurate parameter readings, which were crucial as the system's response relied on them. The tests successfully demonstrated the accuracy and reliability of the system by utilizing the Internet of Things as a data transfer channel. The system's reliability was assessed and found to be 100% reliable in accurately responding to motor faults. It is important to note that this study focused solely on electrical faults in the monitoring system. The researchers recommend including other types of defects, such as mechanical and environmental issues, to reduce human effort and extend the lifespan of industrial motors. To enhance the system's capabilities, the researchers suggest using a three-phase power source instead of just a variable frequency drive. Additionally, the project cost could be reduced by replacing the microcontroller with a smaller and more capable device like an Integrated Circuit (IC) or a microcontroller with a built-in Wi-Fi module such as the Raspberry Pi. The researchers also

propose testing the system's capability to monitor multiple motors simultaneously. For improved functionality, they suggest incorporating a larger database to store history logs and error logs, allowing previous logs to be accessed through the mobile application. Furthermore, the ability to turn the motor on and off at any time via the mobile application would be beneficial. Finally, the researchers recommend developing a feature that enables the system to anticipate motor failures in advance.

Acknowledgment

The researchers would like to express their heartfelt gratitude to Mapua Malayan Colleges Laguna (MMCL) for their invaluable support and encouragement in publishing this research project. The unwavering support provided by MMCL has allowed the researchers to pursue their endeavors and achieve international publication. The researchers are grateful for the guidance, resources, and expertise that have significantly contributed to the success of this research project.

REFERENCES

- Baldonado, M., Chang, C.-C.K., Gravano, L., Paepcke, A.: The Stanford Digital Library Metadata Architecture. *Int. J. Digit. Libr.* 1 (1997) 108–121
- Bruce, K.B., Cardelli, L., Pierce, B.C.: Comparing Object Encodings. In: Abadi, M., Ito, T. (eds.): *Theoretical Aspects of Computer Software. Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, Vol. 1281. Springer-Verlag, BerlinHeidelbergNew York (1997) 415–438
- van Leeuwen, J. (ed.): *Computer Science Today. Recent Trends and Developments. Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, Vol. 1000. Springer-Verlag, BerlinHeidelbergNew York (1995)
- Michalewicz, Z.: *Genetic Algorithms + Data Structures = Evolution Programs*. 3rd edn. Springer-Verlag, BerlinHeidelbergNew York (1996) Elmore, W.A. 2004, *Protective Relaying Theory and Application*, NY
- Farag, W. A. and Kamel, Mi.I, 1999. Microprocessor-Based Protection Sysyem for Thre-Phase Induction Motor Protection System Using PIC Microcontroller,6(2), 2018 DOI.2321-0613
- Katakwar, G., Sawarbandhe, M., Jenekar, P. and Ali S. Three-phase induction Motor Protection system by using a PIC Microcontroller. 6(2), 2018th ser. Doi:2321-0613
- Uyar, O, and Cunkas, M. 2012. Fuzzy Logic-based Induction Motor Protection System. *Neural Computing and Applications*, 23(1),31-40. Doi:10.1007/s0051-012-0862-0
- Cusido, J., Rosero, J., Garcia, A., Ortega J., and Romeral, L. 2007. Online System for Fault Detection in Induction Machines Based on Wavelet Convolution. 2007 IEEE (Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers) Instrumentation & Measurement Technology Conference IMTC 2007. Doi:10.1109/imtc.2007.379106
- Chatterjee, Mitra, Mahatta, S. and Kareddy, S. 2009. A novel Solid State Integrated Protection System for Three-Pahse Induction Motors, vol.8,92-93.
- Chudsama, H., Parmar, B., Ranwa P.< and Tank, V., 2016. Induction Motor Protection using a Microcontroller. *International Journal of Science and Engineering*,2(08). doi:2349-784
- Madakam, S., Ramaswamy, R., and Tripathi, S. 2015. Internet of Things (IoT): A Literature Review. *Journal of Computer and Communications*, 03(05), 164-173. Doi:10.4236/jcc.2015.350